

Indivisible Effective Dynamics of Coarse-Grained Observers

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Abstract

Recent work has shown equivalence between the formal apparatus of quantum mechanics and a general class of non-Markovian systems called *indivisible stochastic systems*. This short paper demonstrates how these indivisible dynamical systems can be used to describe the effective dynamics of coarse-grained observers. The observation suggests that quantum mechanics may arise as the expected phenomenology of coarse-grained systems in a classical, deterministic substrate.

Consider a deterministic system of microscopic states x . Suppose a coarse-grained observer does not have access to the microscopic states, but only to coarse-grained configurations $C(x)$. Importantly, the observer does not know which coarse-graining they inhabit.¹

Generally speaking, any transition law between observed configurations cannot factor as a Markov process

$$P(C_2 | C_1) P(C_1 | C_0) \neq P(C_2 | C_0), \quad (1)$$

because any observed configuration C_t does not uniquely determine the microscopic state (Zwanzig, 1961; Mori, 1965). In other words, $P(C_2 | C_0)$ cannot be divided into the steps $P(C_2 | C_1) P(C_1 | C_0)$, because the coarse-graining procedure loses information not captured in any C_t . This is conceptually the analog of the transition operator seen in Barandes 2025b:

$$\Gamma(t_2 \leftarrow t_0) \neq \Gamma(t_2 \leftarrow t_1) \Gamma(t_1 \leftarrow t_0). \quad (2)$$

Notice that if we could sum over all potential microstates $r \in R(C_0)$ compatible with C_0 , we could give

$$P(C_2 | R(C_0)) = \sum_{r \in R(C_0)} P(C_2 | r) P(r | C_0). \quad (3)$$

When considering all substrate possibilities, divisibility returns. It's the coarse-graining itself that leads to the indivisibility. Now consider if we observe the configuration C_1 at some intervening time, we can limit the compatible set of microstates to some new $R(C_0, C_1) \subset R(C_0)$

$$P(C_2 | R(C_0, C_1)) = \sum_{r \in R(C_0, C_1)} P(C_2 | r) P(r | C_0, C_1). \quad (4)$$

where $P(C_2 | R(C_0, C_1)) \neq P(C_2 | R(C_0))$. The effective observer-level dynamics remain indivisible, because the intervening observation C_1 changes the applicable set of microstates.

¹The important aspects of this setup are the classical substrate (cf. 't Hooft 2016; Adler 2004) and observer-relative features (cf. Zurek 2003; Rovelli 1996; Fuchs et al. 2014). There are clear forerunners, but the specific formulation is new.

We can read the addition of C_1 as an observation or “measurement”. The indivisibility is induced by the addition of coarse-grained information in the intermediate state.²

This observation suggests that the recognition of equivalence between indivisible stochastic systems and quantum mechanical ones (Barandes, 2025a,b) may be pointing to a candidate ontology. If indivisible stochastic mechanics are the effective phenomenology of coarse-grained observers, the previously shown “stochastic-quantum correspondence” (Barandes, 2025b) alludes to a chain of reasoning that follows

Coarse-grained observers \rightarrow Indivisible stochastic mechanics \rightarrow Quantum phenomenology.

In other words, quantum phenomenology may be the *expected* phenomenology for coarse-grained observers, including those which inhabit classical, deterministic dynamical systems.

Illustrative Example

This section will draw out an example for the purposes of illustration. It should not be confused as a derivation or reconstruction of quantum mechanics, but it will show structural parallels. Although the substrate I’ve used is a deterministic antisymmetric system, the unistochastic correspondence (Barandes, 2025b) guarantees that any system that can be described with unistochastic dynamics can be dilated into a system that evolves unitarily in Hilbert space.

Consider a classical, deterministic system whose microscopic state $x \in R^2$ evolves according to

$$\dot{x} = Ax, \quad A = \begin{pmatrix} 0 & -\omega \\ \omega & 0 \end{pmatrix}. \quad (5)$$

The matrix is real antisymmetric, describing a rotation centered on the origin

$$x(t) = R(\omega t) x(0). \quad (6)$$

This is a circular trajectory that preserves norm $|x|$. Although this kind of norm-preserving substrate may be natural for a quantum system, the unistochastic theorem would suggest that it is not a required property.

Now consider a coarse-grained observer which cannot access the state x directly, but instead sees labels $C(x) \in 0, \dots, K-1$ which indicate one of K sectors the trajectory is divided into equally. Each sector has width $2\pi/K$.

If τ is a coarse-grained time interval between observations, then each step unfolds a rotation $\alpha = \omega\tau$. The transition probability from an initial sector i to a resulting sector j is the fraction of sector i that rotates into sector j under the rotation $R(\alpha)$.

For generic α not a multiple of the sector width $2\pi/K$, exactly two adjacent sectors receive the rotated wedge. We can break down the angle of rotation α into an integer number of whole sectors rotated through m and a fractional portion f we have $\alpha = (m + f) \cdot 2\pi/K$. With this decomposition we can write the transition matrix as

$$\Gamma_{ji}(\tau) = \begin{cases} 1 - f & \text{when } i = j + m \pmod{K} \\ f & \text{when } i = j + m + 1 \pmod{K} \\ 0 & \text{otherwise.} \end{cases} \quad (7)$$

²Related work has begun to study divisibility and indivisibility under coarse-graining and uncertainty (Pimenta, 2025); the present note proposes coarse-grained observer uncertainty itself as the source of indivisible effective dynamics.

Note the two non-zero entries.

Now notice that the transition matrix $\Gamma(2\tau)$ would have to be reconstructed by decomposing the new α into m and f ; the resulting matrix will similarly have two non-zero entries. However, if the coarse-grained observer's effective dynamics only unfold in steps τ , the equivalent interval would need be described effectively as $\Gamma(\tau) \cdot \Gamma(\tau)$.

$$[\Gamma(\tau) \cdot \Gamma(\tau)]_{ji} = \begin{cases} (1-f)^2 & \text{when } i = j + 2m \pmod{K} \\ 2f(1-f) & \text{when } i = j + 2m + 1 \pmod{K} \\ f^2 & \text{when } i = j + 2m + 2 \pmod{K} \\ 0 & \text{otherwise.} \end{cases} \quad (8)$$

This resulting transition matrix has 3 non-zero entries, and therefore the effective dynamics are indivisible.

$$\Gamma(2\tau) \neq \Gamma(\tau) \cdot \Gamma(\tau) \quad (9)$$

The intuitive picture is natural. The initial wedge is known but the observer has uniform uncertainty over where within that wedge the starting condition is. Evolving forward an uncertain initial state will carry compounding uncertainty in the final state, spreading the potential outcomes over multiple positions.

The counterbalance to this uncertainty in the final result is that *as the configurations at each step have been observed* the uncertainty in the starting condition can be narrowed to a smaller and smaller wedge. The entropy in observed configurations C_0, \dots, C_t actually drives the increase in precision for the observer's knowledge of the initial position. With each observed configuration C_t , the set R of compatible substrate realizations condenses.

$$R(C_0) \supset R(C_0, C_1) \supset R(C_0, C_1, C_2) \supset \dots \quad (10)$$

In our case, the width of compatible substrate wedges shrinks.

Now if we take a more geometric approach to the problem, we can consider the probability as an overlap between the indicator functions χ_i for each sector i where

$$\chi_i(\theta) = \begin{cases} 1 & \text{when } \theta \text{ in sector } i \\ 0 & \text{otherwise.} \end{cases} \quad (11)$$

Integrating over the circle, the overlap between two χ functions is their inner product, meaning we can express the transition matrix alternatively as

$$\Gamma_{ji}(\tau) = \frac{\langle \chi_i, R(\omega\tau)\chi_j \rangle}{\langle \chi_i, \chi_j \rangle}. \quad (12)$$

The inner product structure is suggestive of the Born rule though not straightforwardly present in its entirety. According to Barandes 2025b, the amplitude $\Theta(\tau)$ can be defined as

$$\Gamma_{ji}(\tau) = |\Theta_{ji}(\tau)|^2. \quad (13)$$

Importantly, this is an *identity*; the dilation Θ is guaranteed to exist (Barandes 2025b via Stinespring 1955). The construction is used to derive Hilbert space, interference, and other quantum phenomena.

Entanglement

Now consider another observer of the same substrate. Their coarse-graining gives states $C'(x)$, which is also split into K wedges but is offset by some angle β so that

$$C'(x) = C(R(\beta)x). \quad (14)$$

First, note that the observations are correlated via the substrate. The joint distribution over the observed values does not factor.

$$P(C(x), C'(x)) \neq P(C(x)) \cdot P(C'(x)) \quad (15)$$

Observations from C and C' will mutually reflect within the other's outcomes so that the set of compatible substrate realizations must be $R(C_0, C'_0, C_1, C'_1, \dots)$. Importantly, while the observers' effective dynamics may exhibit locality, there is no necessity that the substrate x or its underlying dynamics A are local. Also note that these observed configurations need not be simultaneous; intervening observations of either observer $C_t(x)$ or $C'_t(x)$ will affect the effective dynamics Γ for the other.

This configuration shows a clear structural analogy to entanglement (Einstein et al., 1935): non-factorizing joint distributions at spatial separation.

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